

Operational Demonstrator of ESD Middleware Milestone MS5

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About this document

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Type: Production of a Prototype – A prototype showing the viability of adaptive storage target selection was developed that works with NetCDF and HDF5 without requiring to change the original application.

Dissemination level: A poster was submitted (approval pending) to a major HPC conference (SC17).

Delivery date Annex 1 (DoA) M24

Means of verifications: The demonstrator consists of three parts: 1) A typical I/O workload that is mimicking checkpoint/restart, 2) a HDF5 VOL Plugin to redirect and persist data to different storage targets and 3) a policy engine that fetches runtime information and adapts the storage target accordingly. For verification of functionality and for performance measurements a NetCDF Benchmark was used, which under the hood uses HDF5 for input/output (I/O), so that data from the application first passes through NetCDF and then through HDF5. In the HDF5 Virtual Object Layer (VOL) I/O calls are intercepted and handled by the ESD demonstrator, which considers runtime information to take a decision on the data target. The following plots show the performance of different I/O targets for the read and write case for different node/processor and data size configurations in comparison to our adaptive approach:

Figure 1: Write performance for different I/O Strategies/Targets. The adaptive tier selector chooses different storage targets depending on a set of policy rules (accounting for node count, processes per node and request size). This adaptive approach can optimize for performance, but the policy rules used for this demonstration read and write to a node local data target for small access (e.g. to avoid network latency or stressing metadata servers) while large amounts of data are directed to parallel file system.

Figure 2: Read performance for different I/O Strategies/Targets. Far adaptive targets the same policy rules as for the write case are applied (which is necessary when using node local storage). The relatively small total data size leads to very similar read performance for all tiers due to caching effects.

The source code for the demonstrator is available with an open source license in a repository on Github: <https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm>

The repository besides the working demonstrator also includes job scripts to reproduce and verify experiments and visualize the results.

Achieved: Yes.